

Synthesis of (\pm)Laggerol

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Laggerol, a new sesquiterpenic secondary alcohol isolated from *Laggeraurita* by Zutshi and Bokadia¹, was assigned structure **1** through chemical degradation and spectral studies. Literature does not seem to record any synthesis of this compound. The present communication describes an unambiguous synthesis of this naturally occurring alcohol.

4-Methyl-1-(1'-propanalethylidene)-3-cyclohexene (**2**) was prepared according to the reported procedure². The aldehyde (**2**) was then subjected to Grignard's reaction with isopropylmagnesium iodide to afford the secondary alcohol (**1**), which on column chromatography over neutral alumina, eluted with 16% benzene in petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) and subsequent distillation under reduced pressure afforded the pure (t.l.c. single spot) laggerol (**1**). The identity of the compound was established through ir and nmr spectra. This provides the first synthesis of (\pm)laggerol.

Experimental

Boiling points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer and

nmr spectra (CCl₄) in a spectrometer (60 MHz) using TMS as internal standard.

To the cooled Grignard reagent (prepared from 200 mg magnesium turnings and 1.5 g isopropyl iodide in anhydrous ether), the aldehyde (**2**; 1 g) diluted in dry ether (10 ml) was added dropwise with stirring. It was then allowed to stand at room temperature overnight and then refluxed for 30 min. The cooled reaction mixture was then decomposed with saturated solution of ammonium chloride. The product was extracted with ether, washed with water and dried. The solvent was removed and the residue purified through column chromatography over neutral alumina (eluting with 16% of benzene in petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°)) and subsequent distillation under reduced pressure gave the alcohol (**1**), b.p. 115–16°/5–6 mm (lit. 109°/3–4 mm) (Found: C, 80.92; H, 11.72. C₁₅H₂₆O requires: C, 81.02; H, 11.79%); R_f = 0.75 (solvent system: benzene-petroleum ether, 1:4); ν_{\max} 3435, 2950, 2900, 2860, 1650, 1385, 1370, 1170, 890, 870 and 795 cm⁻¹; δ 0.82–1.0 (6H, d, isopropyl), 1.60 (6H, s, vinylic methyls), 1.90 (6H, bs, allylic methylenes), 3.3 (1H, α to hydroxy) and 5.2 (1H, CH=C).

References

1. S. K. ZUTSHI and M. M. BOKADIA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1976, **14**, 64.
2. O. P. VIG, B. RAM, C. P. KHERA and J. CHAND, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 955.

